

THE INITIAL SCHOLARLY PHENOMENON AND EARLY INTELLECTUAL IMPULSES OF PROFESSOR QALLY AYIMBETOV

Aymbetov Allambergen Maxet uli

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20646202>

Abstract. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the socio-historical, ethno-geographical, and psychological foundations underlying the formation of Professor Qally Ayimbetov, the founder of Karakalpak folkloristics, as a scholar and intellectual. Drawing upon his autobiographical memoir *Echoes of Bygone Days*, the study examines the social stratification of Karakalpak society in the early twentieth century, the cultural and economic significance of the Chimbay region, and the influence of modernization processes on the development of the scholar's worldview and intellectual consciousness.

Keywords: Qally Ayimbetov, folkloristics, Chimbay, social environment, ethnography, memoir realism, *The Tyrant King*, Abu Bakir Divayev.

Professor Qally Ayimbetov, the founder of Karakalpak folkloristics, emerged as an intellectual figure during a period of profound social and historical transformation in Central Asia at the beginning of the twentieth century. The study of this period requires not only the examination of biographical facts but also a comprehensive analysis of the ethno-social structure, geographical environment, and cultural-spiritual conditions of Karakalpak society. Such an approach is of considerable scholarly significance.

Qally Ayimbetov was born on March 20, 1908, in the village of Aralbay, located northwest of Turym Bridge in the Chimbay region. At that time, the Chimbay area occupied the right-bank territories of the Amu Darya, bordering the Khanate of Khiva in the south and the Aral Sea region and adjacent settlements of present-day Kazakhstan in the north. Historically, this territory served as an important center of caravan routes, intercultural exchange, and commercial interaction.

Ayimbetov's memoir *Echoes of Bygone Days* represents a rare and valuable source that realistically reflects the lifestyle, social structure, and historical transformations of the Karakalpak people in the early twentieth century. In this work, the author describes various aspects of social life, ranging from the internal organization of Karakalpak villages to urban culture and occupational classifications.

In his recollections, the scholar divides the people of that period into major occupational categories. This classification remains highly significant for contemporary ethno-sociological research. Artisans, craftsmen, traders, and service providers are portrayed as the principal economic force responsible for sustaining everyday life and generating material wealth within society.

Ayimbetov's childhood was marked by severe hardship. Recalling those years, he wrote that after the death of his father, only a single goat remained in the household, and its modest milk supply helped his mother keep him alive during the years of famine. He and his mother lived alone, and every evening she told him folk tales.

His mother, Palzada Adil qizi, became the first spiritual educator in his life. Despite the hardships of famine, she enriched her son's inner world through folk narratives. Among these stories, the tale *The Tyrant King* became particularly influential, providing the young Ayimbetov with his first understanding of social injustice. The tale recounts how a cruel ruler, seeking to punish a widowed woman, burned her young son alive before her eyes.

Overwhelmed by grief, the mother is said to have dissolved into water and vanished. This tragic narrative left a lasting impression on the future folklorist.

The story resonated deeply with Ayimbetov because it reflected elements of his own experience: the loss of his father at an early age and the difficult life he shared with his mother.

Although he had endured hunger and poverty, he had not yet encountered the extreme manifestations of cruelty described in the tale. Soon afterward, his mother passed away, leaving him an orphan at the age of thirteen. Nevertheless, the story remained firmly embedded in his memory and continued to shape his understanding of injustice.

A decisive turning point in Ayimbetov's intellectual development came when he entered the Russian-Native School in Chimbay. Although such schools were originally established to serve the colonial interests of the Russian Empire, they objectively provided local youth with access to secular education and modern knowledge. During his studies, he became acquainted with editions of Turkic epic literature published by the prominent Turkologist and folklorist Abu Bakir Divayev (1855–1933), including *Alpamysh*, *Koblandy*, *Kyz Zhibek*, and other epics in Kazakh and Tatar.

Through these works, Ayimbetov encountered narratives centered on justice and injustice, good and evil, oppression, loyalty, friendship, betrayal, and other fundamental human conflicts.

He came to understand that truth ultimately prevails. As a result, he finally found an answer to the question that had long troubled him after hearing the tale *The Tyrant King* from his mother. The complexity of epic narratives sparked a deep intellectual curiosity and ultimately influenced the direction of his future scholarly research.

The editions of *Alpamysh* and *Koblandy* published by Divayev in Tashkent and Orenburg between 1890 and 1910 represented some of the highest achievements of Turkic folkloristic scholarship of that era. These publications were not merely collections of texts; they also constituted some of the earliest examples of the scholarly classification and systematization of folklore materials.

Teachers at the Russian-Native School recognized Ayimbetov's growing interest in folklore. Consequently, he was sent to study at the Pedagogical Technical School established in Turtkul in 1925. Along with other talented students, he continued his educational journey there.

This represented the first major step in his acquisition of professional education.

Two principal factors played a decisive role in shaping his personality and scholarly outlook. The first was his familial and social environment. The traditional upbringing he received in Aralbay village, together with the aspirations of his maternal uncle Adil, who wished that the boy would become a *biy* (a traditional community leader and arbitrator), instilled in him a strong sense of responsibility and leadership from an early age. The second factor was psychological trauma and compensatory development. Losing his father at the age of five, his mother at thirteen, and enduring famine forced him to confront the realities of life at a profound level. The tale *The Tyrant King* served not merely as a literary work but as a stimulus for understanding broader social realities.

The memoir further documents the modernization processes taking place in Chimbay.

Technological innovations, including the appearance of the French Renault Sahara automobile and the first airplane—referred to locally as the “air ship”—are described in a realistic manner, without literary embellishment. Reports published in the newspaper *Erkin Karakalpakstan* indicate that during the campaign “Support for the Airplane” in 1926–1927, local people contributed money, livestock, and even borrowed resources to support technological

progress. These facts demonstrate the positive attitude of the Karakalpak population toward modernization and scientific advancement.

The memoirs also devote considerable attention to customs, folk beliefs, traditions, and everyday life. These materials reveal the cultural environment that later contributed to Ayimbetov's development as a professional folklorist.

Based on the analysis of the socio-historical factors shaping Ayimbetov's personality, several conclusions can be drawn. First, his memoirs are grounded in the principles of realism.

Historical events and technological developments are presented objectively and without artistic distortion, making the memoirs a reliable historical source. Second, his classification of occupations and descriptions of Chimbay's markets function as a kind of "ethnographic encyclopedia" of Karakalpak society in the early twentieth century. Third, through references to historical figures such as Allayar Dosnazarov and through descriptions of public attitudes toward technological progress, the memoir documents the dynamics of national awakening and modernization among the Karakalpak people.

It should also be emphasized that Ayimbetov's early interest in traditions, customs, beliefs, and oral folklore laid the foundation for his future scholarly work in collecting and systematizing the national folklore heritage. The autobiographical realism of *Echoes of Bygone Days* is especially valuable because it presents modernization not through political rhetoric but through the sincere and objective perspective of childhood perception, thereby preserving an authentic picture of the period.

In conclusion, the phenomenon of Qally Ayimbetov lies in his ability to interpret personal tragedy through the universal narratives of oral tradition. This capacity enabled him to become not merely a collector of folklore materials but a scholar capable of understanding their deeper social and philosophical meanings. **[Translator's note: the original term "теолог-қәниге" requires clarification in the source text; it may be more accurately rendered as "scholar" or "intellectual specialist" rather than "theologian."]** Ultimately, Ayimbetov's intellectual evolution was the result of the organic synthesis of ethno-cultural traditions, social challenges, and educational influences, which later enabled him to establish the foundations of Karakalpak folkloristic studies.